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THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN KAZAKHSTAN'S CONTEMPORARY FOREIGN POLICY

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Abstract: *The article explores the role of digitalization in shaping the “New Kazakhstan.” Digital technologies are becoming a crucial driver of economic modernization, transparency in public governance, and human capital development. It is emphasized that digitalization fosters the creation of a competitive society based on innovation, openness, and sustainable development. The paper analyzes key directions of digital transformation, including e-government, digital infrastructure, IT sector growth, and the development of citizens’ digital competencies.*

Keywords: *digitalization, New Kazakhstan, innovation, public governance, sustainable development*

Currently, states are striving to develop new digital technologies in the context of the transition to an information and communications society. This trend is the most prevalent in contemporary international relations. Digitalization has become a necessary component in the development strategy of all leading countries worldwide. Today, a country's level of development and its role in the international system depend on relevant knowledge and access to new digital technologies. Scientific and technological progress is a tool for human development, because at each stage of technological development, humanity transitions from one management method to new, more efficient ones. This can be illustrated by the transition from one energy source, more expensive and dirtier, to cleaner and more efficient ones, from heavier and more fragile materials to lighter, stronger, more flexible, and more durable ones, all while human knowledge, skills, and competencies grow and expand. Each stage of technological and social cycles triggers conflict between older generations and the work methods they used, and new generations, their new tools and methods. Then comes new growth, new jobs appear, production volumes increase, and the complexity of the work performed increases.

Economist K. Perez in his book "Technological Revolutions and Financial Capital" notes that since the end of the 18th century, humanity has experienced five technological revolutions, each of which generated a technological wave, accompanied by the spread of the achievements of technological revolutions in the form of new equipment and technologies. The duration of each wave was approximately 50 years. This period is determined by the peculiarities of the functioning of the link between financial capital and the innovative capabilities of new technology. The exhaustion of a technological wave deprives the economy of development drivers and leads to a crisis, from which the economy emerges thanks to the next wave. According to K. Perez, “a change in the technological paradigm is necessarily accompanied by a change in the forms of financing and a change in social

relationships of adequate innovations not only in the production sphere - in products and methods of organization, but also in finance and institutions” [1].

The Industrial Revolution creates not only new social relations and political institutions. It creates a new culture, a new world. How exactly technology determines social relations is determined by historical experience. Let us recall what enormous social changes were caused by such a small technical innovation as the appearance of a stirrup on the side of a horse. It was the stirrup that made the rider stable in the saddle and determined the complete military superiority of the knight over the footsoldier. This led to the era of feudalism, the time of the reign of knights. The mechanism of action of the technological factor is as follows. A fundamental discovery gives a decisive advantage to the people "chosen by God", who begin a wave of military expansion. Peoples who do not want to become victims of the conqueror, copy their technology, infrastructure, crafts, industry. Then - customs, culture, social orders. The last technological revolution was associated with the invention of the microcircuit in 1961, on the basis of which modern television, mobile communications, personal computers and the Internet were created.

The essence of technological and economic changes, marking the transition to a new level of development, is as follows: a change in resources and tools at a person's disposal, a change in generations and their skills, abilities, and competencies. Now humanity is at the beginning of the fourth industrial revolution. This stage is characterized by the development of information technology, the penetration of the Internet into all spheres of the economy, the development of the ecosystem of the Internet of things and related artificial intelligence technologies. There are three categories of states. The first is the elite, those who create knowledge. The second are those who, based on new knowledge, create technologies for themselves and for the first group. The third are those who will provide the first two groups with resources: human, raw materials, energy. We need to decide where we are. Of course, we do not want to remain a raw materials appendage. But in order not to fall into technological slavery, we need to develop science, create technologies, and implement them in production. If earlier a billion people claimed the level of the European middle class, now there are already six billion. To ensure the growth of the standard of living of such a large number of people, fundamentally new methods of creating tools and producing energy are needed.

In addition, we must not forget about another important social phenomenon that the digital era provides. It provides greater transparency of the world, openness and accessibility of technologies, the possibility of obtaining any education, any consultation. In other words, anywhere in the world it will be possible to print a thing on a 3D printer and sell it through a global Internet platform.

Digitalization can make a breakthrough in economic development and become the main driver of growth. The 4th intelligent control element is being introduced. Man, gradually moved towards this. He converted documents into electronic form, learned to work with them, and now the stage of managing machines and production processes has come. The United States of America at one time officially proclaimed that additive manufacturing would be the tool for achieving global US superiority.

In fact, additive manufacturing is the harbinger of a new technological revolution. These technologies provide thirty times the productivity advantage, in addition to huge savings in energy costs, in the use of material. In 2004, Facebook was registered, and in 2007, the iPhone appeared. These two events became catalysts for a whole series of technologies that bring efficiency to industrial capital.

Let's try to analyze these effects. The widespread use of information technology in working with logistics companies has led to the fact that the goods that the plant manufactures for the client are at the plant for forty minutes. As a result of changing production processes, Harley Davidson has reduced the production cycle from 21 days to six hours (every 89 seconds a motorcycle rolls off the assembly line, fully customized for its future owner). In industrial areas, communication between machines is expanding; machines report which consumables they are running low on, when repairs will be needed, how many parts will be manufactured in the next hour. Sensors and portable devices in many industries

monitor the condition and location of equipment, where workers are located. Workers monitor the level of gas pollution in mines, and the optimization of repair crews.

The GLONASS system is coming into practice, when a car itself gives an alarm signal in case of an accident, soon gadgets will be installed in the fields that will monitor the state of the harvest. There is already a technology of virtual and augmented reality, when you can point a smartphone at a historical building and see what it was like a hundred years ago. Technologies called "product life cycle management" are appearing in design, when you can not only design a product, but also understand how long it will serve, which of its properties are costly, from the point of view of investments. New opportunities for companies are opening up big data processing technologies. Growing computer power allows us to process large amounts of data, predicting important business events. For example, seismic data processing helps oil companies predict oil migration and significantly increase the extraction coefficient. Real miracles await us with the development of so-called machine learning technologies, artificial intelligence and robotics [2].

Analysts note that the transfer of production to countries with cheap economies will save up to 65% on labor costs, replacing human employees with robots can reduce costs by 90%. If the previous wave of Internet development (late 1990s - early 2000s) affected mainly "light" segments, the markets closest to the Internet (media, telecom, retail), now the Internet is conquering "heavy" industrial and infrastructure sectors and regulated and specialized markets, medicine and education. The involvement of surrounding objects in the global Internet space is called the "Internet of Things" (IoT). This is a system of unified computer networks and connected physical objects (things) with built-in sensors and software for collecting and exchanging data, with the ability to remotely monitor and control in an automated mode, without human intervention. This is a smart city (Smart City), smart energy (Smart Energy), telemedicine, smart home, smart roads.

The period up to 2025 is very important, because during this period the foundations of a new stage of human development, great transformations in the economy, politics, social sphere and culture are laid. The digital is accelerated industrialization based on new technologies, it is improvement of human capital, it is effective public administration. In October 2017, the Supreme Economic Council of the EAEU adopted the "digital agenda" until 2025. III modernization is innovation, emphasis on IT technologies. Digitalization will cover the agro-industrial complex, energy, mining and oil and gas sectors, transport and logistics. Digitalization of agriculture, transition to a digital structure of the agricultural market. This can become a stage in the development of resource potential, smart technologies, transition to a green economy. The EAEU should become the world's breadbasket.

Globalization as a modern form of international world order imposes much stricter requirements on the state for socioeconomic viability and fit into more complex structures of international relations. Thus, the global economy is increasingly opening up for Kazakhstan and this is also part of the new reality, which contains many challenges and opportunities for improving the professionalism and activity of Kazakhstanis. The country is entering, as Udartsev S. aptly put it, "dense layers of the atmosphere - a historical era of increasingly tough economic, scientific and technical competition, where there are no weak ones, but only strong and even stronger and the strongest [3].

The foreign policy agenda for the development of sovereign Kazakhstan currently includes a move toward digitalization and innovation, which is the primary response to the challenges of the modern and future world. The primary goal of the "Digital Kazakhstan" state program is the progressive development of the digital ecosystem to achieve sustainable economic growth, enhance the competitiveness of the economy and the country, and improve the quality of life of the population. The "Digital Kazakhstan" state program will be implemented in four key areas: the implementation of the Digital Silk Road, which includes the development of a reliable, high-speed, and secure digital infrastructure; and the development of a creative society. This also includes developing competencies and skills for the development of the digital economy, improving digital literacy among the population, training ICT specialists for industry,

and digital transformation across economic sectors. This is the widespread implementation of digital technologies to enhance the competitiveness of various sectors of the economy; the transition to a proactive government. This is the improvement of electronic and mobile governance systems, and the optimization of the provision of public services [4].

Conclusions

1. Technological revolutions function as cyclical drivers of economic and social transformation, restructuring institutions, finance, and governance systems.
2. The Fourth Industrial Revolution marks a qualitative shift toward digital ecosystems, artificial intelligence, and integrated cyber-physical production systems.
3. Global technological competition increasingly determines geopolitical hierarchies and national sovereignty.
4. Digitalization enhances transparency, accessibility of knowledge, and economic efficiency, while simultaneously intensifying global competition.
5. Kazakhstan's strategic priority lies in transitioning from a resource-based economy to an innovation-driven digital model to secure long-term competitiveness and avoid technological dependency.

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